

ON THE FLEXURAL TEST METHOD OF ADVANCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with a new flexural test method of advanced composites. Although the conventional three- or four-point bending test is convenient, it has several disadvantages especially for advanced composites. A newly proposed method is based on a bending by means of axial compression and this method overcomes the above disadvantages.

A set of testing device has been designed and machined and various kinds of composites have been tested. It has been made clear that the new method is suitable especially for high performance composites such as T800/epoxy.

INTRODUCTION

In these years advanced composite materials are widely used especially for aerospace applications. New fibers with very high performance are also being developed. For example, T800 carbon fiber of Toray Company has the tensile strength of 5GPa; this fiber is already commercially available. Further, T1000 with the strength higher than T800 has been developed. Although new materials requires new testing methods, testing methods for advanced composites are not necessarily complete. Many of current methods are just duplicates of testing methods for conventional metals or plastics. A flexural test method is one of them.

Three- or four-point bending test is commonly used to evaluate the flexural strength of advanced composites. Although these tests are easy to operate, they include some disadvantages.

First, a stress concentration takes place around a loading nose of three- or four-point bending. This leads the stress distribution far from that predicted by an elementary beam theory[1]. Thus a beam is apt to fail at the loading nose due to this stress concentration. This effect is large for composites because composite materials have strong anisotropy and they tend to fail in a brittle manner.

Next, the failure load is affected by the loading condition. For example, if some plies of soft sheets (such as polypropylene) are inserted in between the test specimen and the loading nose, the failure load increases[2]. It will probably be due to the fact that the inserted sheets (cushion) reduce the stress concentration and friction between the loading nose and specimen. Although this idea of sheet insertion can be used to get more reasonable flexural strength, the optimum condition has not been established.

In the present paper, apart from conventional three- or four-point bending, a new flexural test method is proposed. This idea is based on a kind of buckling; this may be called a "compression-bending" method.

PRINCIPLE

Consider a bar with rectangular cross section (width= b , thickness= t) and both ends being pin supported as shown in Fig.1. When some axial load, P , is applied to it, the bar will deform. Denoting the deflection at midspan A be δ , the bending moment at point A becomes

$$M = P\delta \quad (1)$$

and the skin stress (bending stress) is

$$\sigma_b = \frac{6M}{bt^2} \quad (2)$$

Therefore the bending strength becomes

$$\sigma_{b,max} = \frac{6M_{max}}{bt^2} \quad (3)$$

where M_{max} is the bending moment at failure at point A . Thus if we measure P and δ in the experiment, bending strength can be calculated from eq.(3).

Since no loading device is attached at the location of maximum bending moment, no stress concentration due to loading nose will occur. On the other hand, the following compressive stress is generated in the specimen:

$$\sigma_c = \frac{P}{bt} \quad (4)$$

If the value of eq.(4) is large, the present method is not suitable for evaluating the bending strength. Another point to be kept in mind is that Young's modulus can not be measured by the present method.

Fig.1 Schematic view of compression bending

Fig.2 Loading device

**DESIGN AND MACHINING
OF TEST DEVICE**

A new testing device must be developed to practice the above idea. First, to realize a pin support condition at both ends of a specimen, a set of loading devices (chuck) was designed (see Fig.2). One device is attached to the crosshead of an Instron type testing machine and the other device, to the bed. The upper device is screwed into a load-cell which is fixed to the crosshead. Ball-bearings are embedded between inner part and outer cover of each device so as to assure rotation-free of the inner part. A specimen is inserted into a spline cut which has been machined at the inner part.

When some load is applied, the point A of Fig.1 goes downwards by the amount $y/2$ where y is the movement of crosshead. Therefore it becomes necessary to develop another device by which the maximum deflection of a specimen can always be measured. To this end, a device shown in Fig.3 was designed. The upper column (upper rack) is attached to the crosshead and the lower column (lower rack), to the bed. Two racks are connected through a gear and a displacement transducer is attached to the gear. By doing this way, the downward movement of the gear becomes always the half amount of the movement of the crosshead. Thus, the displacement transducer always indicates the deflection at the midpoint of the specimen, as far as the specimen deforms symmetrically.

Fig.3 Device to measure maximum deflection

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SPECIMENS AND TEST PROCEDURE

1. Test specimen

Specimens tested here are advanced composites with unidirectional prepreg sheets of Toray T300 and T800 carbon fiber. Tensile strengths of these fibers are about 3GPa and 5GPa, respectively. The matrix is 177 C cure epoxy resin. Laminated plates were made in an autoclave. A summary of materials is shown in Table 1. In the notation, the alphabets U and Q represent unidirectional and quasi-isotropic, respectively, and the numerals 8 and 3 stand for T800 and T300 carbon fibers.

Table 1 Material data of composites tested here

fiber	matrix	stacking seq.	notation	thick.	V_f (%)
Torayca T800	177 C cure epoxy #3631	(0) ₁₆	U8	2.24	60.0
		(0/±45/90) ₂₅	Q8	2.22	60.0
Torayca T300	177 C cure epoxy #3601	(0) ₁₆	U3	2.16	60.0
		(0/±45/90) ₂₅	Q3	2.21	60.0
cure: autoclave. non-bleed processing					

In the experiment both the compression-bending and the ordinary four-point bending have been carried out. Three kinds of length ($L=100, 150, 200\text{mm}$) were selected for compression-bending and span length of either $L=75\text{mm}$ or 90mm was used for four-point bending. The width of the specimen, b , was fixed to 15mm for both cases. Number of specimens was six for each case.

2. Test procedure

The setting of a test specimen for compression-bending is as follows: When a test specimen is attached to the bending device, the displacement transducer should come to the center of the specimen. To do so, a set of ring-shaped spacers with various thickness was prepared and some appropriate spacers were inserted in between the crosshead and loading device. This adjustment is needed only one time at the setting of the device; after that, no adjustment is necessary even when the length of the test specimen is changed. In this compression-bending test, the deflection of the specimen is fairly large. Then a displacement transducer with long stroke (50mm or 100mm) was used.

After all setting was finished, a compressive load was applied with the following crosshead speed: 2.5mm/min for specimens of $L=100\text{mm}$, 5mm/min for $L=150\text{mm}$, and 10mm/min for $L=200\text{mm}$; these crosshead speeds were selected arbitrarily.

The four-point bending was carried out under the loading location of $L/3$ and the crosshead speed of 5mm/min .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Bending test

With increasing applied load, some sound was heard at a little before the apparent failure. Although this sound might indicate microcracks, they could not be observed by a naked eye.

Figure 4 is the surface and side view of the fractured specimens. All specimens made of T300 carbon fiber (U3, Q3) failed at the tension side, whereas Q8 specimens began to fail from the compression side. As for U8 specimens, failure mode could not be observed because one specimen broke into many small pieces instantaneously. But it is supposed that the failure of U8 specimens started at the compression side.

Fig.4 Typical failure mode of advanced composites

Fig.5 Load- and moment-deflection curves

Solid lines in Fig.5 shows typical load-deflection curves of the advanced composites for L=100mm. Dashed lines are calculated from eq.(1). Although load-deflection curves tend to saturate, moment-deflection curves increase monotonically. Thus it is not difficult to calculate the maximum moment at the failure, M_{max} . Other specimens with different length showed similar feature. In the case of L=150mm, the maximum deflection was about 32mm and for specimens of L=200mm, the deflection reached up to 55mm. This is the reason why a long-stroke displacement transducer was used.

2. Results

Figure 6 is the summary of the flexural strength. Test results by means of four-point bending are also shown in this figure. Each open mark is the average of compression-bending data and solid marks show the average of test data by means of four-point bending. Each vertical range indicates the scattering of six test specimens. The coefficient of variance (standard deviation/average) was in between 2.5% and 10.1%. Although the length of specimen should affect the bending strength, evident tendency was not obtained in the present experiment; for some specimens, the bending strength increased with increasing the length of specimen, and for some specimens, it decreased.

As has been discussed before, compressive stress is inevitably generated in the specimen. Figure 7 shows the degree of compressive stress compared to bending stress of advanced composites.

3. Discussion

Figure 6 shows that, for U3 and Q3 composites, the bending strength by means of compression-bending test is almost the same as that of four-point bending. This indicates that both methods can be applied for composites with moderate properties.

But the situation is different for T800 carbon composites which have super high strength. According to Fig.6, the bending strength of U8 composites by means of four-point bending is too small, even smaller than that of U3 composites. The tensile strength of T800 carbon bundle is about 5GPa whereas that of T300 is about 3GPa. Therefore, the tensile strength of

Fig.6 Comparison of bending strength between compression-bending and four-point bending

Fig.7 Ratio of compressive stress to bending stress

U8 and U3 unidirectional composites should be 3 and 1.8 GPa, respectively, if the rule of mixtures is applied. It is said that the compressive strength of T800 composite is smaller than the tensile strength whereas the tensile and compressive strengths of T300 composites are almost the same. The bending strength may be affected by the compressive strength as well as the tensile strength. Nevertheless, it is very peculiar that the bending strength of T800 composites is rather smaller than that of T300 composites. This fact indicates that the four-point bending is not suitable for T800 composites. This may be due to the undesirable effect of loading nose, i.e., stress concentration around the loading nose.

On the contrary, fairly high strength is attained by the use of compression-bending method. This evidence holds for Q8 composites also. Therefore, it may be concluded that the compression bending method is desirable for composites with very high strength fiber such as U8 or Q8.

As is shown in Fig.7, the effect of compressive stress is less than 2% if the length of specimen is larger than 150 mm. Therefore, this effect may be neglected.

CONCLUSIONS

A new bending test method was proposed in this paper. This method is based on a bending by means of axial compression. Since no loading device is attached at the failure region of a specimen, this method overcomes undesirable effects of loading nose.

Based on this idea, a device was designed and machined. Using this device, compression-bending test of CFRP was tried.

It has been made clear that this method is superior to the conventional method especially for super-high strength composites like T800 composites. This evidence will become more serious for T1000 composites. Composites with pitch-based carbon fiber have, in general, relatively smaller compressive strength and therefore, the effect of loading nose is serious. Thus the new method may be suitable for pitch-based carbon fiber composites also.

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